

Some theorem on common fixed points and points of coincidence for mappings in metric space

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Abstract.

The paper includes theorem giving the sufficient condition for existence of common point of coincidence and common fixed point for $2n + 1$ mappings in metric space.

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Introduction

Let (X, d) be a metric space. By contraction ([3], [4]) we understand a mapping $F : X \rightarrow X$ for which there exists $L \in [0, 1[$ such that $d(Fx, Fy) \leq L \cdot d(x, y)$, for all $x, y \in X$. The very good known Banach Fixed Point Theorem reads as follows ([3], [4]). Let X be a complete metric space with metric d . Let $F : X \rightarrow X$ be a contraction. The above suppositions imply the existing of a fixed point, the solution of $Fx = x$. The Banach Fixed Point Theorem is an important tool in mathematical analysis and has been investigated under various conditions and developed in different directions. Among others, many authors consider a variety of contractive conditions (see for example [5], [6], [7], [8]). In the presented paper we obtain a sufficient condition for existence of common fixed points and points of coincidence for $2n + 1$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) mappings in metric space (X, d) . The condition which is given in the paper is analogous to condition included in [2] and named by authors - Kannan type condition. Summarizing, we will prove theorem giving sufficient condition (Kannan type condition) for existence of common fixed point for $2n + 1, n \in \mathbb{N}$ mappings $X \rightarrow X$ where (X, d) is a metric space.

1 Notations, definitions, lemma

Definition 1.1. ([7], [1]) A mapping $T : X \rightarrow X$ - for a metric space (X, d) - is called Kannan if there exists $\alpha \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$ such that for all $x, y \in X$

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \alpha[d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty)]$$

Definition 1.2. A point $y \in X$ is called point of coincidence of a family $\{T_j\}_{j \in J}$ of self-mappings on X if there exists a point $x \in X$ such that $y = T_j x$ for all $j \in J$.

Definition 1.3. A pair (F, T) of self-mappings on X is said to be weakly compatible if $FTx = TFx$ whenever $Fx = Tx$.

The lemma below is a generalization of the result from the paper [1].

Lemma 1.4. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let X be a nonempty set and the mappings

$$F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$$

have a unique point of coincidence v in X . If all pairs (F, T_i) , (F, S_i) , for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ are weakly compatibles, then v is the unique common fixed point of mappings $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$.

Proof. Take $u \in X$ such that $Fu = S_1u = \dots = S_nu = T_1u = \dots = T_nu = v$. By weakly compatibility of all pairs (F, T_i) , (F, S_i) , for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ we have

$$\left(S_i v = S_i F u = F S_i u = F v, \quad \text{and} \quad T_i v = T_i F u = F T_i u = F v \right), \quad \text{for } i \in 1, \dots, n.$$

Therefore the point w such that $w = Fv = S_1v = \dots = S_nv = T_1v = \dots = T_nv$ is a point of coincidence for mappings $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$, so $w = v$ by uniqueness. From the above v is a unique common fixed point of mappings $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$. $\square$

Definition 1.5. Let (X, d) be a metric space. Let $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n : X \rightarrow X$ be the mappings such that $S_i(X) \cup T_i(X) \subset F(X)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$. We define the sequence $\{x_m\}_{m \geq 0}$ of elements of X as follows. Choose an arbitrary point x_0 in X . Let x_1, x_2 be the point of X such that $Fx_1 = T_1x_0$ and $Fx_2 = S_1x_1$. Continuing, $Fx_3 = T_2x_2$ and $Fx_4 = S_2x_3, \dots, Fx_{2n-1} = T_nx_{2n-2}, Fx_{2n} = S_nx_{2n-1}$. Generally, if we have defined x_{kn} for a $k \in \{0, 2, 4, \dots\}$, we put

$$Fx_{kn+i} = \begin{cases} T_{\frac{i+1}{2}}x_{kn+i-1}, & \text{for } i \in \{1, 3, \dots, 2n-1\}, \\ S_{\frac{i}{2}}x_{kn+i-1}, & \text{for } i \in \{2, 4, \dots, 2n\}. \end{cases}$$

2 Main theorem

Theorem 2.1. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and

$$F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$$

be self mappings of the space (X, d) such that $F(X)$ is the closed subset of X and $\bigcup_{i=1}^n S_i(X) \subset F(X)$, $\bigcup_{i=1}^n T_i(X) \subset F(X)$. Let us suppose that the following condition is satisfied:

$$d(S_i x, T_j y) \leq A_i d(Fx, S_i x) + B_j d(Fy, T_j y), \quad \text{for } i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (2.1)$$

for all $x, y \in X$ where A_i, B_j are non-negative real numbers with $A_i + B_j < 1$, for $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$ have a unique point of coincidence. If additionally all pairs $(F, T_i), (F, S_i)$, for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ are weakly compatibles, then $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$ have the unique common fixed point.

Proof. Firstly, we will prove that, if $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$ have a point of coincidence, then it is unique. Assume that v, v^* are two distinct point of coincidence for mappings $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$. Then, there exists u, u^* such that

$$Fu = S_1u = \dots = S_nu = T_1u = \dots = T_nu = v$$

and

$$Fu^* = S_1u^* = \dots = S_nu^* = T_1u^* = \dots = T_nu^* = v^*.$$

By (2.1) we have

$$d(v, v^*) = d(S_1u, T_1u^*) \leq A_1d(Fu, S_1u) + B_1d(Fu^*, T_1u^*) = 0,$$

so $v = v^*$. We will prove the existence of a point of coincidence of mappings $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$. Choose an arbitrary point x_0 in X . The sequence $\{x_m\}_{m \geq 0}$ of elements of X is defined by Definition 1.5. Let us consider two cases:

- a) there exists $k \in \{0, 2, 4, \dots\}$ for which $Fx_{kn} = Fx_{kn+1}$.
- b) for every $k \in \{0, 2, 4, \dots\}$ $Fx_{kn} \neq Fx_{kn+1}$.

In the case a) - by (2.1) - for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ - we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(S_i x_{kn}, Fx_{kn}) &= d(S_i x_{kn}, Fx_{kn+1}) = d(S_i x_{kn}, T_1 x_{kn}) \\ &\leq A_i d(Fx_{kn}, S_i x_{kn}) + B_1 d(Fx_{kn}, T_1 x_{kn}) \\ &= A_i d(Fx_{kn}, S_i x_{kn}) + B_1 d(Fx_{kn}, Fx_{kn+1}) \\ &= A_i d(Fx_{kn}, S_i x_{kn}) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} d(Fx_{kn}, T_i x_{kn}) &= d(S_n x_{kn}, T_i x_{kn}) = \\ &\leq A_n d(Fx_{kn}, S_n x_{kn}) + B_i d(Fx_{kn}, T_i x_{kn}) \\ &= B_i d(Fx_{kn}, T_i x_{kn}). \end{aligned}$$

This yields that the point y defined as

$$y := Fx_{kn} = S_1 x_{kn} = S_2 x_{kn} = \dots = S_n x_{kn} = T_1 x_{kn} = T_2 x_{kn} = \dots = T_n x_{kn}$$

is the required unique point of coincidence for mappings $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$.

In the case b) the reasoning is as follows. Let $k \in \{0, 2, 4, \dots\}$. We have $Fx_{kn} \neq Fx_{kn+1}$. By (2.1) we get

$$d(Fx_{kn}, Fx_{kn+1}) = d(S_n x_{kn-1}, T_1 x_{kn})$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq A_n d(Fx_{kn-1}, S_n x_{kn-1}) + B_1 d(Fx_{kn}, T_1 x_{kn}) \\ &= A_n d(Fx_{kn-1}, Fx_{kn}) + B_1 d(Fx_{kn}, Fx_{kn+1}). \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} d(Fx_{kn}, Fx_{kn+1}) &\leq \frac{A_n}{1 - B_1} d(Fx_{kn-1}, Fx_{kn}) \\ &\leq \lambda d(Fx_{kn-1}, Fx_{kn}), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$0 < \lambda := \max \left\{ \frac{A_i}{1 - B_j}, \frac{B_j}{1 - A_i} : i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \right\} < 1.$$

Moreover

$$\begin{aligned} d(Fx_{kn}, Fx_{kn-1}) &= d(S_n x_{kn-1}, T_n x_{kn-2}) \\ &\leq A_n d(Fx_{kn-1}, S_n x_{kn-1}) + B_n d(Fx_{kn-2}, T_n x_{kn-2}) \\ &= A_n d(Fx_{kn-1}, Fx_{kn}) + B_n d(Fx_{kn-2}, Fx_{kn-1}). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} d(Fx_{kn}, Fx_{kn-1}) &\leq \frac{B_n}{1 - A_n} d(Fx_{kn-1}, Fx_{kn-2}) \\ &\leq \lambda d(Fx_{kn-1}, Fx_{kn-2}). \end{aligned}$$

From the above we get easily for any $m \in \mathbb{N}$

$$d(Fx_m, Fx_{m+1}) \leq \lambda^m d(Fx_0, Fx_1)$$

and for any $m_2 > m_1$

$$\begin{aligned} d(Fx_{m_1}, Fx_{m_2}) &\leq d(Fx_{m_1}, Fx_{m_1+1}) + d(Fx_{m_1+1}, Fx_{m_1+2}) + \dots + d(Fx_{m_2-1}, Fx_{m_2}) \\ &\leq [\lambda^{m_1} + \lambda^{m_1+1} + \dots + \lambda^{m_2}] d(Fx_0, Fx_1) \\ &\leq \left[\frac{\lambda^{m_1}}{1 - \lambda} \right] d(Fx_0, Fx_1), \end{aligned}$$

so $(Fx_m)_{m \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Let us define $v := \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} Fx_m$. Since $F(X)$ is a closed subset of X then there exists $u \in X$ such that $F(u) = v$. Let $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. We have for a $k \in \{0, 2, 4, \dots\}$ and $i_0 \in \{2, 4, \dots, 2n\}$

$$\begin{aligned} d(Fu, T_j u) &\leq d(Fu, Fx_{kn+i_0}) + d(Fx_{kn+i_0}, T_j u) \\ &= d(Fu, Fx_{kn+i_0}) + d(S_{\frac{i_0}{2}} x_{kn+i_0-1}, T_j u) \\ &\leq d(Fu, Fx_{kn+i_0}) + A_{\frac{i_0}{2}} d(Fx_{kn+i_0-1}, S_{\frac{i_0}{2}} x_{kn+i_0-1}) \\ &\quad + B_j d(Fu, T_j u). \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$d(Fu, T_j u) \leq \frac{1}{1 - B_j} d(Fu, Fx_{kn+i_0})$$

$$+ \frac{A_{i_0}}{1 - B_j} d(Fx_{kn+i_0-1}, Fx_{kn+i_0}),$$

so for sufficiently large k - the distance $d(Fu, T_j u)$ can be arbitrarily small, then $T_j u = Fu$, for any $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Moreover

$$d(Fu, S_j u) = d(S_j u, T_j u) \leq A_j d(Fu, S_j u) + B_j d(Fu, T_j u) = A_j d(Fu, S_j u),$$

whence $S_j u = Fu$, for any $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. We have proved that v is a unique point of coincidence of mappings $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$. If additionally all pairs $(F, T_i), (F, S_i)$, for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ are weakly compatibles, then by Lemma 2.1, $F, S_1, \dots, S_n, T_1, \dots, T_n$ have the unique common fixed point. $\square$

3 Examples

Example 3.1. Let $X = [0, \infty[$ and d be the Euclidean metric on X . Let $n = 2$. We define the mappings $F, S_1, S_2, T_1, T_2 : X \rightarrow X$ as follows:

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} -\frac{7}{2}x + 21, & \text{for } x \in [0, 4], \\ 7, & \text{for } x \in [4, 7], \\ -\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{21}{2}, & \text{for } x \in [7, 21], \\ 0, & \text{for } x \in [21, \infty[. \end{cases}$$

and for $i = 1, 2$

$$S_i(x) = \begin{cases} (1 + \frac{1}{2i})x + i, & \text{for } x \in [0, 4], \\ 7, & \text{for } x \in [4, \infty[, \end{cases}$$

$$T_i(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2i}x + i + 4, & \text{for } x \in [0, 4], \\ 7, & \text{for } x \in [4, \infty[. \end{cases}$$

We have $F(X) = [0, 21]$, $S_i(X) = [i, 7]$, $T_i(X) = [i + 4, 7]$, for $i = 1, 2$. We put $A_1 = A_2 = \frac{1}{2}$ and $B_1 = B_2 = \frac{1}{3}$. One can easily observe that the condition (2.1) is satisfied. For $x_0 = 2$ - by Definition 1.5 - we get the sequence $(Fx_m)_{m \in \mathbb{N}}$ as follows: $-14, 6, 7, 7, 7, \dots$. So $v = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} Fx_m = 7$ is a unique point of coincidence of mappings F, S_1, S_2, T_1, T_2 . Since all pairs $(F, T_i), (F, S_i)$, for $i \in \{1, 2\}$ are weakly compatibles, then - by Lemma 2.1 - $v = 7$ is the unique common fixed point for mappings F, S_1, S_2, T_1, T_2 . Moreover, let us remark that if we change definition of the function F as follows

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} -\frac{7}{2}x + 21, & \text{for } x \in [0, 4], \\ 7, & \text{for } x \in [4, 7[, \\ 6, & \text{for } x = 7, \\ -\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{21}{2}, & \text{for } x \in]7, 21], \\ 0, & \text{for } x \in [21, \infty[, \end{cases}$$

then there is no common fixed point for mappings F, S_1, S_2, T_1, T_2 . Since $7 = F(4) = S_1(4) = S_2(4) = T_1(4) = T_2(4)$, the point 7 is only the point of coincidence of a family F, S_1, S_2, T_1, T_2 . In this case the condition (2.1) is still satisfied but all pairs $(F, S_i), (F, T_i)$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$ are not weakly compatibles.

Example 3.2. Let $X = [0, \infty[$ and d be the Euclidean metric on X . Let $n = 3$. We define the mappings $F, S_1, S_2, S_3, T_1, T_2, T_3 : X \rightarrow X$ as follows:

$$F(x) = x, \text{ for } x \in X.$$

and for $i = 1, 2, 3$

$$S_i(x) = \begin{cases} 3 - x^{i+1}, & \text{for } x \in [0, 1], \\ 2, & \text{for } x > 1. \end{cases}$$

$$T_i(x) = \begin{cases} 3 - x^{i+4}, & \text{for } x \in [0, 1], \\ 2, & \text{for } x > 1. \end{cases}$$

We have $F(X) = X$, $S_i(X) = T_i(X) = [2, 3]$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$. We put $A_1 = A_2 = A_3 = \frac{1}{2}$ and $B_1 = B_2 = B_3 = \frac{5}{12}$. One can easily observe that the condition (2.1) is satisfied. For $x_0 = \frac{1}{2}$ - by Definition 1.5 - we get the sequence $(Fx_m)_{m \in \mathbb{N}}$ as follows: $\frac{1}{2}, \frac{95}{32}, 2, 2, 2, \dots$. So $v = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} Fx_m = 2$ is a unique point of coincidence of mappings $F, S_1, S_2, S_3, T_1, T_2, T_3$. Since all pairs (F, T_i) , (F, S_i) , for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are weakly compatibles, then - by Lemma 2.1 - $v = 2$ is the unique common fixed point for mappings $F, S_1, S_2, S_3, T_1, T_2, T_3$.

Example 3.3. Let $X = [\frac{1}{4}, 4]$ and d be the Euclidean metric on X . Let $n = 2$. We define the mappings $F, S_1, S_2, T_1, T_2 : X \rightarrow X$ as follows:

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{x}, \text{ for } x \in X$$

and for $i = 1, 2$

$$S_i(x) = x^{\frac{1}{i+3}}, \quad T_i(x) = x^{\frac{1}{i+1}}.$$

All the pairs (F, T_i) , (F, S_i) , for $i \in \{1, 2\}$ are weakly compatibles. If we put $A_1 = A_2 = \frac{1}{4}$ and $B_1 = B_2 = \frac{5}{8}$ then the condition (2.1) is satisfied. By Definition 1.5 starting from $x_0 = 2$ we obtain the sequence $(Fx_m)_{m \in \mathbb{N}}$ as follows: $\frac{1}{2}, 2^{\frac{1}{2}}, 2^{-\frac{1}{8}}, 2^{\frac{1}{24}}, 2^{-\frac{1}{120}}, \dots$, whence $v = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} Fx_m = 1$ is the unique common fixed point for mappings F, S_1, S_2, T_1, T_2 .

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